

THE IMPORTANCE OF LIBRARY CULTURE IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF RESPONSIBILITY

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ANNOTATION

The article presents information on the need to create a sense of spirituality and the role of the culture of reading in youth.

Key words. Spirituality, state policy, belonging, society, reading, development.

During the years of independence in our country, large-scale work was carried out to educate young people to be spiritually mature and physically healthy, patriotic and selfless, and to protect their rights and interests. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" was adopted in order to fundamentally improve the activity in this field and raise it to a new level of high quality. This decree clearly shows the actions that should be taken in order for young people to solve problems and find their place in the life of society.

Instilling in the minds and hearts of young people a sense of responsibility for the development of the country and the future of the country was considered one of the priority tasks ahead of us. In order to fulfill these tasks rationally, it is important to develop a sense of belonging among young people. Living with a sense of belonging to the events happening around us is one of the most urgent issues of today, said Islam Karimov, the First President of Uzbekistan.

Responsibility is education that forms the obligation to fulfill one's duty to the generations. There are different forms of feeling of belonging in human life. Civil concern, moral concern, social concern, etc.

Civil involvement - involvement in some activity, process is partnership. If every citizen lives with a sense of personal involvement in the fate of the Motherland, his duty and responsibility to the society will also increase. In this situation, the students have the ability to sense the moods and interests of the people around them, as well as to work on the skills of understanding the mood and interests of the people around them. An idea is formed about the means of achieving the goal. In the situation of the experience, the teacher confronts the students with the reality of some kind of spiritual decline. This situation is emotional (the student imagines how difficult it is for him), logical (looking for the best ways to solve the situation), as well as active (determining his attitude and determining the direction of his behavior in this situation). occurs in levels. From the definitions given to the sense of belonging, we can understand that this concept is of great importance in every aspect of social life.

Spirituality is not an exception. Spirituality is a complex concept that expresses the maturity and humanity of a person. In order for a person to develop a sense of belonging in a spiritual sense, it is necessary to carry out systematic actions. Young people who have managed to embody the feeling of spiritual belonging would contribute to the preservation of high human qualities in front of the nation and the future generation.

Our first presenter, Islam Karimov, defined the concept of spirituality in the work "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" as follows: Spirituality is something that calls a person to spiritual purification and spiritual growth, awakens a person's inner world, strengthens his will, and awakens his faith. The incomparable power of 'shooting' is the criterion of all his visions. In fact, spirituality is an important component of human life and lifestyle. The process of becoming spiritual and spiritually mature prepares the ground for the formation of spiritual involvement.

Reading culture is an important component of these systematic works. The President of our republic, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said about this: by reading a book, you can find a solution to all the problems that may arise.

From the words of the great thinker Alisher Navoi, who said that every second of reading a book brings you closer to wisdom, you can understand how important the role of reading culture is in human life and spiritual maturity.

Whether we refer to the great masterpieces of our national heritage, modern literature of today, or examples of world literature, all of these can become an important factor in forming a spiritual worldview and a source of education. There are many observations today about the positive and negative aspects of the era of globalization. Egocentrism, vandalism, becoming a traitor to the country is considered a painful situation, but the fact that this situation is on the rise among young people is even more painful. The root cause of such situations is directly related to the level of spiritual maturity and involvement.

It is necessary to read books, to turn to literature that can serve as an example, serves for thinking, and contains ideas that encourage a person to grow. There are many factors in the life of young people that can interest them, attract them and penetrate their minds and worldviews. At the same time, their number is increasing. Whether we realize it or not, our youth are under the influence of such factors. Because some of them do not have a shield to eliminate such malicious situations, moral immunity has not yet been formed. Bookshelves today are full of useful, spiritual development and personal growth books. So, today we cannot say enough with quantitative indicators of books. In order to improve the results, in addition to organizing various contests, organizing book readings in the family, educational institutions, and workplaces and organizing meetings with the leading representatives of our literature will help to eliminate the problem.

In order to ensure that young people who have a strong interest in the Internet enter the world of books from the virtual world and to achieve the stability of this journey, it is necessary to form a conscious attitude because they read books. The creation of electronic versions of fiction books is a positive solution to this problem. However, we have so many heritages that have not been made into electronic form that it is difficult to achieve spiritual maturity and spiritual relevance without reading them.

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